

N3C Query Report:

Healthcare Utilization

Abstract

This query quantifies the number of visits a person has within their N3C healthcare system in the year after their covid index date. Visits are quantified for patients stratified by predicted PASC status. Emergency department and inpatient visits are low for people both with and without PASC. Outpatient utilization is higher for people with PASC. Over the year timeframe, there is a decrease in the number of visits for people both with and without PASC.

Methods

Inclusion criteria

- **Study period:** 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2022
- **Age:** Any age
- **COVID-19 positive:** via a qualifying index event between 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2021
 - Definition 1. Positive SARS-CoV-2 PCR test (no antibody tests)
 - Definition 2. Diagnosis of COVID-19 via 1 inpatient or 2 outpatient instances of ICD-10 code U07.1
- **Pre-covid utilization:** 2 or more visits with the healthcare system within the year before the index event

Data is from release version 82 of the N3C data enclave, released on June 23rd, 2022. Site-level quality filters were applied prior to analysis in order to remove 9 of the 74 data partners with significant and systematic missingness according to the following criteria: sites (1) should not shift dates by more than 30 days, (2) should have serum creatinine and lymphocyte count results for at least 25% of hospitalizations, and (3) should not have >10% of their hospitalizations where the COVID-19 index date is more than 200 days after the visit start date.

Definitions

Index event

The earliest instance of COVID-19 positivity between 3/1/2020 – 4/30/2021. A patient's first COVID positivity is defined by either Definition 1 or 2 above (lab-based or diagnosis-based).

Time period

The analysis starts 1 month after the index event, therefore the first month analyzed is considered month #2 after the index event.

Outpatient, Inpatient, ED visit

Visits were classified as outpatient, inpatient or ED visits based on visit_concept_id. A complete list of concepts for visit type is included in the appendix.

Diagnosis of PASC

PASC was defined as previously described¹, trained on a cohort of patients who were known to have a u09.9 diagnosis. In order to label a patient as having PASC or not, the patient must meet the following criteria: (1) they must be at least 18 years old, (2) they must have at least 2 days of data in the system, (3) they must have at least one diagnosis and one medication in the pre- or post-index period, and (4) they must have data at least 90 days since the covid index. Approximately 10% of patients with valid COVID index dates do not have sufficient data to determine if they have PASC.

Cell size and patient privacy protection

In order to comply with N3C data use policies, any cell sizes under 20 were suppressed and the surrounding row and column data were adjusted with small gaussian noise in order to obfuscate the suppressed counts.

Results

An accounting of the patients meeting our inclusion criteria for COVID positivity is shown below for each cohort. Of the 13,731,822 patients in the site-filtered cohort described above (from 74 sites), 2,246,955 qualified for the analysis by meeting definition one or two for COVID positivity, and 1,753,022 patients qualified by meeting two or more visits in one year before index date. Based on the non-harmonized definition of PASC, there are 93,622 patients with PASC, 940,922 patients with no PASC and 718,431 patients with no prediction.

The average age of the overall cohort was 43 years old, however the machine learning model used to predict PASC status does not predict for people under the age of 18, contributing to the younger average age of the no PASC prediction group (36 years). Of those who did receive a prediction, the PASC group has an average age of 54, while the non-PASC group has an average age of 48. With the exception of the no prediction group, the cohort is majority female. The cohort is majority non-hispanic white.

Table 1. Characteristics of patients by PASC status

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	PASC Status		
		With PASC # (%)	Without PASC # (%)	No PASC prediction # (%)
Age groups				
Mean age	43	54	48	36
<1	10184 (0.58)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	10184 (1.42)
1-4	27859 (1.59)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	27859 (3.88)
5-9	38142 (2.18)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	38142 (5.31)
10-15	71867 (4.1)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	71867 (10.0)
16-20	122608 (6.99)	1371 (1.46)	54067 (5.75)	67170 (9.35)
21-35	406724 (23.2)	10777 (11.51)	224813 (23.89)	171134 (23.82)
36-45	253024 (14.43)	14505 (15.49)	147251 (15.65)	91268 (12.7)
46-55	263996 (15.06)	19672 (21.0)	161867 (17.2)	82457 (11.48)
56-65	248221 (14.16)	20641 (22.04)	160224 (17.03)	67356 (9.38)
66+	310397 (17.71)	26696 (28.5)	192707 (20.48)	90994 (12.67)
Sex				
Male	770362 (43.94)	29350 (31.34)	375485 (39.91)	366524 (51.02)

Female	981546 (55.99)	64426 (68.79)	566471 (60.2)	351917 (48.98)
Other/Missing/Unknown	1114 (0.06)	<20	190 (0.02)	920 (0.13)
Race ethnicity				
Non-Hispanic white	1077532 (61.47)	58406 (62.36)	605101 (64.31)	414025 (57.63)
Non-Hispanic black	213665 (12.19)	15490 (16.54)	120998 (12.86)	77177 (10.74)
Hispanic	258920 (14.77)	12016 (12.83)	124990 (13.28)	121914 (16.97)
Non-Hispanic Asian	45182 (2.58)	2238 (2.39)	24615 (2.62)	18329 (2.55)
Non-hispanic Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	2067 (0.12)	141 (0.15)	1186 (0.13)	740 (0.1)
Other non-Hispanic	40174 (2.29)	658 (0.7)	11158 (1.19)	28358 (3.95)
Missing/Unknown	115482 (6.59)	4713 (5.03)	52881 (5.62)	57888 (8.06)
Deceased within a year of the index event	40653 (2.32)	1795 (1.92)	11369 (1.21)	27489 (3.83)

Table 2. Total visit volume over time period by PASC status

Utilization metric	Patients with PASC			Patients without PASC			Patients with no prediction		
	N (#)	Mean (SD)	Median	N (#)	Mean (SD)	Median	N (#)	Mean (SD)	Median
Inpatient visits	68250	0.73 (1.97)	0	279897	0.3 (1.21)	0	34767	0.05 (0.41)	0
Distinct inpatient days	364396	3.89 (12.8)	0	1135085	1.21 (6.43)	0	157845	0.22 (3.23)	0
Outpatient visits	3615736	38.6 (53.59)	22	14027905	14.91 (24.39)	8	2133348	2.97 (8.43)	0
Distinct days with outpatient visits	2382390	25.44 (25.13)	18	10228874	10.87 (13.84)	6	1717208	2.39 (5.97)	0
ED visits	79580	0.85 (2.8)	0	387769	0.41 (1.45)	0	67323	0.09 (0.5)	0
Distinct days with ED visits	62154	0.66 (2.02)	0	312927	0.33 (1.1)	0	57571	0.08 (0.4)	0

Table 3. Total visit volume over the time period by sex in patients with PASC

Visit type	Male			Female		
	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)
Inpatient visits	26519	0	0.9 (2.28)	41724	0	0.65 (1.81)
Outpatient visits	1158776	22	39.53 (58.89)	2455791	23	38.17 (50.92)
ED visits	25099	0	0.86 (2.92)	54481	0	0.85 (2.74)

Table 4. Total visit volume over the time period by race ethnicity in patients with PASC

Visit type	White Non-Hispanic			Asian Non-Hispanic			Black Non-Hispanic			Hispanic		
	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)
Inpatient visits	38982	0	0.67 (1.84)	1224	0	0.55 (1.72)	15964	0	1.03 (2.41)	8985	0	0.75 (2.09)
Outpatient visits	2331111	23	39.91 (55.48)	78558	21	35.1 (45.84)	615810	23	39.76 (53.04)	401854	21	33.44 (48.55)
ED visits	48305	0	0.83 (2.38)	1045	0	0.47 (1.32)	16948	0	1.09 (3.48)	8500	0	0.71 (2.26)

Visit type	Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander Non-Hispanic			Other Non-Hispanic			Unknown		
	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)	N (#)	Median	Mean (SD)
Inpatient visits	55	0	0.39 (0.88)	446	0	0.68 (1.64)	2594	0	0.55 (1.71)
Outpatient visits	5454	23	38.68 (49.17)	29254	24	44.46 (67.07)	153695	19	32.61 (42.87)
ED visits	99	0	0.7 (1.47)	539	0	0.82 (2.14)	4144	0	0.88 (5.54)

Figure 1a. Graph of total monthly visit volume by PASC status

Figure 1 shows all visits, colored by visit type, in the year after the index date. The first month of acute infection is excluded. People predicted to not have PASC have a steeper decrease in visits, while people predicted to have PASC show a slower decrease in visits.

Figure 1b. Graph of monthly visit percent by PASC status

Figure 1b shows visits counts as a percent of visits during the year time period for that PASC group. The slower decline in visits for people with PASC is easily shown, although a similar percent of visits occur in the later months for people with and without PASC.

Figure 2a. Monthly visit volume summary for patients with PASC

Figure 2 shows the median (with 25-75 percentile) number of visits a person has in each month after their index date. While there are outliers with likely implausible amounts of visits, the median inpatient and ED visits are at 0 for all PASC statuses.

Figure 2b. Monthly visit volume summary for patients with PASC, y-axis zoomed to 15

Figure 2b shows the median (with 25-75 percentile) number of visits a person has in each month after their index date. The y-axis has been limited to more easily see the median outpatient visits for people with and without PASC.

Discussion

We find that people with PASC have higher outpatient utilization (mean 38.6 visits, with 25.4 distinct days) than inpatient (mean 0.73 visits, with 3.89 distinct days) or ED (mean 0.85 visits, with 0.66 distinct days) utilization. Utilization for people without PASC is also higher for outpatient (mean 14.97 visits, with 10.87 distinct days) compared to inpatient (mean 0.3 visits, with 1.21 distinct days) or ED (mean 0.41 visits, with 0.33 distinct days) visits. On average, utilization is lower for people without PASC when compared to people with PASC. People with no prediction have the lowest utilization, although as expected outpatient (mean 2.97 visits, with 2.39 distinct days) is still higher than inpatient (mean 0.05 visits, with 0.22 distinct days) or ED (mean 0.09 visits, with 0.08 distinct days).

PASC outpatient utilization remains higher than inpatient or ED utilization regardless of gender (table 3) or race (table 4) demographic. Outpatient utilization is similar between male (mean 39.53 visits) and female (38.17) patients. There were differences in utilization by race and ethnicity, with lower mean outpatient visits in Asian Non-Hispanic (35.1) and Hispanic (33.4) than White Non-Hispanic (39.91) people, higher mean inpatient visits in Black Non-Hispanic (1.03) and Hispanic

(0.75) compared to White Non-Hispanic (0.67) people and higher mean ED visits in Black Non-Hispanic (1.09) compared to White Non-Hispanic (0.83) people. In addition to reporting the mean of visit counts, we also include median, which is less affected by outliers with very high visit counts that may represent unreliable data. While lower than mean counts, the same trends remain present.

Our concept set for outpatient visits includes Outpatient Laboratory Visit (ID 32253), which may contribute to a higher number of outpatient visits. This included concept set may indicate a distinct outpatient record which would actually be a part of an outpatient visit already counted, potentially overcounting some outpatient visits.

Overall visit counts decrease with time (figure 1, figure 2) for people with PASC as well as the people without PASC. There is a sharper decrease in visits for people without PASC. Visits remain fairly consistent across the 11 month study timeframe for people without a prediction, with a slight increase in the number of visits starting around the 10th month. People may stop seeking medical care for a number of reasons, including cost concerns, time investment, being otherwise difficult to access, unfavorable physician care, and low perceived need². Fatigue and the cardinal symptom of ME/CFS, post-exertional malaise, are commonly reported post-COVID symptoms for SARS-CoV-2 survivors, and 1 in 2 patients met the diagnosis criteria for myalgic encephalomyelitis/chronic fatigue syndrome (ME/CFS) after infection^{3,4,5,6}. In a study on chronic fatigue syndrome utilization, ME/CFS patients reported higher barriers and were more likely to delay or forgo medical treatment⁷. The CDC estimates half of ME/CFS patients stop pursuing medical care, despite still being ill⁸.

The computable phenotype for PASC from our ML model uses outpatient utilization as a prediction feature, and requires visits post-index to make a prediction. Outpatient utilization is the fourth most important feature in prediction, biasing people with higher utilization to have a PASC prediction. We therefore reran the analysis using only u09.9 diagnosis code as indication of PASC. The analysis of u09.9 diagnosis revealed similar trends to the analysis run on the ML model PASC predictions (Table 1 and Table 2 for u09.9dx included in appendix). This may further indicate bias in who receives a u09.9 diagnosis. Additionally, this analysis may focus on people with higher utilization by including only people with two or more visits in the year prior to their index date.

Limitations

The visit counts available for people only reflects visits within N3C sites and may not accurately count all visits for a person. Additionally, the cohort as a whole only represents patients seeking care at sites providing data to N3C, and not the general US population.

The definition that includes a PCR positive test may disproportionately represent those with test access and documented tests, which excludes many from the first wave before testing was available, and possibly three quarters of cases throughout the pandemic⁹ further, PCR false negative rates are higher in certain populations, including women and people under age 40¹⁰.

The present study utilizes our pre-existing ML models for computable phenotyping of PASC, however, our models are being continuously updated as we receive more data from sites with U09.9 codes, improve our methods, and have greater opportunity for clinical validation.

Appendix

Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of patients by u09.9dx status

Characteristic	Overall # (%)	u09.9 Status	
		With u09.9 dx # (%)	Without u09.9 dx # (%)
Age groups			
Mean age	44	51	44
<1	4348 (0.65)	0	4348 (0.65)
1-4	11629 (1.73)	<20	11625 (1.74)
5-9	14384 (2.14)	<20	14377 (2.16)
10-15	25413 (3.79)	36 (0.98)	25377 (3.8)
16-20	43978 (6.56)	69 (1.88)	43910 (6.58)
21-35	159781 (23.82)	529 (14.42)	159261 (23.87)
36-45	98624 (14.7)	662 (18.05)	97967 (14.69)
46-55	103553 (15.44)	818 (22.3)	102740 (15.4)
56-65	98344 (14.66)	828 (22.57)	97521 (14.62)
66+	110705 (16.5)	708 (19.3)	110003 (16.49)
Sex			
Male	293128 (43.7)	1141 (31.11)	291987 (43.77)
Female	377428 (56.27)	2527 (68.89)	374901 (56.2)
Other/Missing/Unknown	203 (0.03)	0	203 (0.03)
Race ethnicity			
Non-Hispanic white	381822 (56.92)	2377 (64.8)	379940 (56.95)
Non-Hispanic black	100695 (15.01)	632 (17.23)	100195 (15.02)
Hispanic	98165 (14.63)	413 (11.26)	97881 (14.67)
Non-Hispanic Asian	17296 (2.58)	74 (2.02)	17248 (2.59)
Non-hispanic Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	1185 (0.18)	<20	1181 (0.18)

Other non-Hispanic	4894 (0.73)	30 (0.82)	4873 (0.73)
Missing/Unknown	66702 (9.94)	149 (4.06)	66642 (9.99)
Deceased within a year of the index event	17971 (2.68)	<20	17947 (2.69)

Supplementary Table 2. Total visit volume over time period by u09.9 status

Utilization metric	Patients with u09.9 diagnosis			Patients without u09.9 diagnosis		
	N (#)	Mean (SD)	Median	N (#)	Mean (SD)	Median
Inpatient visits	1824	0.5 (1.33)	0	171821	0.26 (1.27)	0
Distinct inpatient days	9213	2.51 (10.21)	0	738099	1.11 (6.56)	0
Outpatient visits	138128	37.66 (56.07)	20	8969005	13.44 (29.76)	4
Distinct days with outpatient visits	89863	24.5 (25.64)	16	6101234	9.15 (15.27)	4
ED visits	2344	0.64 (2.23)	0	207652	0.31 (1.47)	0
Distinct days with ED visits	1956	0.53 (1.86)	0	165785	0.25 (1.06)	0

Supplementary Figure 1. Total visit count in 3 month bins

Supplementary Figure 2. Percent of visits in 3 month bins

Supplementary Figure 3a. Visit volume per person in 3 month bins

Supplementary Figure 3b. Visit volume per person in 3 month bins with limited y-axis

Concept IDs for Inpatient/Hospitalization visits

Hospitalization codes	
Concept ID	Concept name
32254	Hospital-Swing Beds
38004282	General Rural Acute Care Hospital
38004290	Military General Acute Care Hospital
38004515	Hospital
262	Emergency Room and Inpatient Visit
32760	Isolation in inpatient setting
8971	Inpatient Psychiatric Facility
581384	Inpatient Nursery
8717	Inpatient Hospital
9201	Inpatient Visit
581379	Inpatient Critical Care Facility

38004276	Chronic Disease Children Hospital
38004281	General Acute Care Children Hospital
38004283	General Acute Care Women Hospital
38004284	Psychiatric Hospital
581383	Inpatient Cardiac Care Facility
38004275	Chronic Disease Hospital Unit
38004279	General Acute Care Hospital
38004280	General Acute Care Critical Access Hospital
32037	Intensive Care
38004288	Military Hospital

Concept codes for Outpatient/Ambulatory visits

Outpatient codes	
Concept ID	Concept name
8716	Independent Clinic
8782	Urgent Care Facility
8947	Comprehensive Outpatient Rehabilitation Facility
8977	Public Health Clinic
32253	Outpatient Laboratory Visit
38003820	Multi-Specialty Group
38004220	Ambulatory Emergency Care Clinic / Center
38004235	Ambulatory Military and U.S. Coast Guard Ambulatory Procedure Clinic / Center
38004239	Ambulatory Multi-Specialty Clinic / Center
38004256	Ambulatory Cardiac Rehabilitation Facility
38004263	Ambulatory Student Health Clinic / Center
38004264	Ambulatory Sleep Disorder Diagnostic Clinic / Center
38004515	Hospital
38004696	Radiation Therapy Center
5084	Off Campus-Outpatient Hospital
8761	Rural Health Clinic
8969	Indian Health Service Provider-based Facility
32693	Health examination

38004216	Ambulatory Community Health Clinic / Center
38004222	Ambulatory Endoscopy Clinic / Center
38004223	Ambulatory Non-Surgical Family Planning Clinic / Center
38004254	Ambulatory Rehabilitation Clinic / Center
8941	Tribal 638 Free-standing Facility
9202	Outpatient Visit
32261	Religious Non-medical Health Care Inst-Outpatient Services
581479	Ambulatory Rehabilitation Visit
38003620	Walk-in Retail Health Clinic
38004208	Ambulatory Family Planning Facility
38004211	Ambulatory Amputee Clinic / Center
38004227	Ambulatory Hearing and Speech Clinic / Center
38004243	Ambulatory Federal Public Health Clinic / Center
38004244	Ambulatory State or Local Public Health Clinic / Center
38004246	Ambulatory Physical Therapy Clinic / Center
38004252	Ambulatory Mobile Mammography Clinic / Center
38004257	Ambulatory Substance Use Disorder Rehabilitation Clinic / Center
8756	Outpatient Hospital
8883	Ambulatory Surgical Center
8966	Federally Qualified Health Center
38003821	Single Specialty Group
38004209	Ambulatory Fertility Facility
38004215	Ambulatory Critical Access Hospital
38004226	Ambulatory Health Service Clinic / Center
38004228	Ambulatory Infusion Therapy Clinic / Center
38004236	Ambulatory Military Outpatient Operational (Transportable) Component Clinic / Center
38004237	Ambulatory Military Ambulatory Procedure Visits Operational (Transportable) Clinic / Center
38004242	Ambulatory Medically Fragile Infants and Children Day Care Clinic / Center
38004247	Ambulatory Primary Care Clinic / Center
38004249	Ambulatory Pain Clinic / Center
38004261	Ambulatory Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Clinic / Center

38004262	Ambulatory Ophthalmologic Surgery Clinic / Center
38004266	Ambulatory VA Clinic / Center
38004267	Ambulatory Occupational Medicine Clinic / Center
38004453	Family Practice
38004693	Clinic or Group Practice
8584	Mobile Unit
8960	Tribal 638 Provider-based Facility
38004225	Ambulatory Genetics Clinic / Center
38004234	Ambulatory Military / U.S. Coast Guard Outpatient Clinic / Center
38004241	Ambulatory Methadone Clinic
38004245	Ambulatory Podiatric Clinic / Center
38004248	Ambulatory Prison Health Clinic / Center
38004250	Ambulatory Radiology Clinic / Center
38004253	Ambulatory Mobile Radiology Clinic / Center
38004258	Ambulatory Recovery Care Clinic / Center
38004260	Ambulatory Rural Health Clinic / Center
8858	Mass Immunization Center
8949	End-Stage Renal Disease Treatment Facility
8968	Indian Health Service Free-standing Facility
581477	Office Visit
38004207	Ambulatory Clinic / Center
38004210	Ambulatory Adult Day Care Center / Clinic
38004213	Ambulatory Augmentative Communication Clinic / Center
38004217	Ambulatory Corporate Health Clinic / Center
38004218	Ambulatory Dental Clinic / Center
38004229	Ambulatory Lithotripsy Clinic / Center
38004240	Ambulatory Medical Specialty Clinic / Center
38004251	Ambulatory Mammography Clinic / Center
38004259	Ambulatory Research Clinic / Center
38004268	Ambulatory Oncology Clinic / Center
38004269	Ambulatory Oncological Radiation Clinic / Center

38004677	Mammography Center
38004702	Indian Health Service facility
8905	Military Treatment Facility
8974	Non-residential Substance Abuse Treatment Facility
581380	Outpatient Critical Care Facility
38004233	Ambulatory Migrant Health Clinic / Center
38004238	Ambulatory Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) Clinic / Center
38004526	Rehabilitation Agency

Concept codes for Emergency Department visits

ED codes	
Concept ID	Concept name
8870	Emergency Room - Hospital
9203	Emergency Room Visit
581381	Emergency Room Critical Care Facility

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